

Presentation

These articles were originally published in the Pedagogy Series, housed in the ISA's Social Justice and Democratization Space in June and October 2021. We are republishing it in order to standardize all the articles in the Sociological Teaching journal, a new space of publication from the Thematic Group 09.

Dear colleagues,

We are pleased to share the second and third issue of the Pedagogy Series, housed on the ISA's Social Justice and Democratization Space. The Pedagogy Series aims to support the global exchange of research and reflections on sociology teaching and sociology pedagogy. This issue features theoretical and reflective pieces from sociologists at various points in their career. Some articles (re)imagine teaching practices for the future, while others look back at lessons from past decades.

Our previous issue (January 2021) focused on sociology educators' analyses of the COVID-19 transition to emergency remote education. This current issue begins with a student perspective on this transition. Undergraduate sociology student Richy Srirachanikorn theorizes experiences of dis/connection in COVID's digital classrooms, culminating in digitized others. Srirachanikorn calls upon sociology instructors to mediate these othering practices in their approaches to digital education.

In our second paper, Rodney Coates critically discusses universities as a colonial institutions. He interrogates structural racism within academia and outlines specific steps for decolonizing the University. Coates ties these decolonial processes to post-secondary curriculum, pedagogies and methodologies, with an emphasis on the power and contestation of Indigenous counter-narratives. Change, Coates reminds us, is possible, but it will require moving past empty slogans. Instead, we

must engage in a radical transformation of the systemic and structural inequities that characterize academic institutions.

Written by Henry Lee Allen, the third article is a reflective piece on the opportunities and constraints, dreams and aspirations, encountered during a 38-year career in teaching sociology across numerous institutions. Allen describes moments of both challenge and joy and concludes by sharing enduring lessons for sociology educators. His message to sociologists is to “Never stop being bold in your teaching, research, and service to all humankind.”

The number also has two papers from India, focusing on the transition to online and blended learning under COVID-19 within the context of India’s 2020 National Education Policy. Rituparna Patgiri draws upon her experience teaching sociology in New Delhi during the pandemic, raising pedagogical questions about student privacy and possibilities for teaching sensitive topics online. Writing from Koraput, sociologist Nupur Pattanaik addresses similar pedagogical shifts through the lens of the digital divide, highlighting challenges faced by students studying in remote locations. Pattanaik emphasizes that the discipline of sociology teaches students and teachers alike to be adaptable to societies in changing circumstances, positioning sociology as a survival resource in this tumultuous period.

Written by Hala Awada, the final article draws links between Lebanon’s severe economic crisis, political system rooted in neoliberal policies and laced with corruption, and the structure of higher education. Taking a lens informed by sociology of education more than scholarship of teaching and learning, Awada examines how the private and public post-secondary systems have responded in unique ways to these broader crises, and with particular implications.

We are grateful for your readership.

Sincerely,

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